

SIMULATION AND TESTING OF STITCHED GLASSFIBRE LAMINATES FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR

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SUMMARY

The goal of this paper is Finite Element (FE) stress analysis of stitched glassfibre composites. The stress distribution gives an idea of laminate fatigue behaviour and potential alarm zone locations. The research includes a Finite Element (FE) simulation and an experimental study for laminates with different stitching parameters. Analysis is performed on meso-level: fiber bundles and matrix are considered, but not separate fibers. Bundle waviness, variable thickness and volume factor are taken into consideration.

Keywords: glassfiber, stitching, finite element analysis, bundle waviness, variable volume factor, homogenization, stress concentration.

LAMINATE STRUCTURE AND STITCHING PARAMETERS

The research object is a laminate made of stitched unidirectional E-glass NCF reinforcement, 0°/90°/M and epoxy resin. Heavy 0° yarns form the actual reinforcing layer, while lightweight 90° and CSM layers exist to increase handling stability. Stitching yarn combines these three layers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Bundles layout and in-plane waviness

Figure 2. Variation of elastic modulus and fibre volume fraction

The laminate consists of two plies of this material, the CSM layers being placed outwards while the 0° yarns are in the middle. The laminate is vacuum infused in stiff mould with the epoxy resin. The stitching can be made dense or sparse with stitching yarn tight or loose. These stitching parameters affect not only the handling and manufacturing convenience but also the fibre bundle waviness, orientation and local elastic moduli (Figure 2). The FE analysis scope is whether this has any effect on laminate stress distribution in linear static. The stress distribution gives an idea of laminate fatigue behaviour and potential alarm zone location.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Direct FE Homogenization Procedure

Figure 3. Laminate cross-section SEM image

Figure 4. Hexagonal structure

Figure 5. Quarter of the periodicity cell

Finite element analysis of the stitched laminate was performed on a meso-level: epoxy matrix and the bundles of fibers are simulated, but not separate fibers. To estimate the effective elastic properties of the bundles a direct homogenization procedure [1] is applied, that allows to replace the heterogeneous microstructure with the effective homogeneous media.

As shown in [2], the chaotic packing of the fibers in the bundle (Figure 3) that is observed in reality, could be correctly replaced by hexagonal packing for simulation purposes (Figure 4). Thus, for the homogenization a unidirectional layer is considered, containing two elastic phases (matrix and fiber), with double-periodic hexagonal packing of fibers. A quarter of periodicity cell (representative volume element) used for homogenization is shown in Figure 5.

The Hook's law for the effective properties of the orthotropic heterogeneous material can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1^* \langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle &= \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle - \nu_{12}^* \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle - \nu_{13}^* \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle \\
 E_2^* \langle \varepsilon_{22} \rangle &= -\nu_{21}^* \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle - \nu_{23}^* \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle \\
 E_3^* \langle \varepsilon_{33} \rangle &= -\nu_{31}^* \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle - \nu_{32}^* \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle \\
 G_{12}^* \langle \gamma_{12} \rangle &= \langle \sigma_{12} \rangle; \quad G_{23}^* \langle \gamma_{23} \rangle = \langle \sigma_{23} \rangle; \quad G_{31}^* \langle \gamma_{31} \rangle = \langle \sigma_{31} \rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In total, 12 effective elastic constants are contained in (1): E_1^*, E_2^*, E_3^* – Young's moduli; $\nu_{12}^*, \nu_{23}^*, \nu_{31}^*, \nu_{21}^*, \nu_{32}^*, \nu_{13}^*$ – Poisson's coefficients; $G_{12}^*, G_{23}^*, G_{31}^*$ – shear moduli. Young's moduli and Poisson's coefficients are connected by relations:

$$E_1^* \nu_{21}^* = E_2^* \nu_{12}^*; E_2^* \nu_{32}^* = E_3^* \nu_{23}^*; E_3^* \nu_{13}^* = E_1^* \nu_{31}^*, \quad (2)$$

The number of independent elastic constants is equal to 9. To estimate the in-plane moduli E_1^*, E_2^* and corresponding Poisson's coefficients, two problems of periodicity cell unidirectional stretching are to be solved. Effective shear moduli are the coefficients connecting macroscopic shear stresses and shear displacements. Therefore, to estimate G_{12}^* it is necessary to solve a problem of periodicity cell in-plane shear.

Moduli G_{23}^*, G_{31}^* are obtained from the solution of longitudinal (antiplane) shear problem.

The procedure of homogenization based on FEM is performed for a quarter of periodicity cell (Figure 5) with fiber volume concentration of 56 %. All the mentioned above problems were solved in ANSYS [3] software. The calculated effective properties of the bundle are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effective elastic moduli of the bundle

Young's moduli, GPa	Shear moduli, GPa	Poisson's coefficient
$E_X = 10.33$	$G_{XY} = 3.81$	$\nu_{XY} = 0.29$
$E_Y = 10.33$	$G_{YZ} = 4.10$	$\nu_{XZ} = 0.07$
$E_Z = 44.13$	$G_{XZ} = 4.10$	$\nu_{XZ} = 0.07$

Local Elastic Coefficients Computation

Figure 6. Non-regular bundles

The meso-scale model should also account for the effect of variation of local elastic moduli due to the higher local fibre volume fraction. Indeed, the bundles thickness may

be variable along the specimen length (Figure 6) because of non-uniform value of the chopped strand tension during laminate manufacturing. The variation of the bundle cross-section area leads to the variation of glassfibre volume factor in the bundle. In order to create the numerical model closest to reality, the real composite specimen was analyzed to measure the bundles thickness in several points. CAD model (Figure 6) and FE model of the bundles with variable cross-section area were developed. Homogenization procedure was carried out for four different fibre volume factors (55%, 58%, 60%, 63%) and approximation curves were constructed for all elastic coefficients. Automated procedure of the local elastic moduli computation (Figure 8) based on the cross-section area (Figure 7) with interpolation of the homogenization results is developed and used for FE structural analysis.

◇Bundle № 1 □Bundle № 2 △Bundle № 3 *Bundle № 4 +Bundle № 5 - -Bundle Vf=56%

Figure 7. Cross-section area variation

Figure 8. Young's moduli variation

Transformation of Lamina Stiffness Matrix

Figure 9. Local coordinate system rotation

In the considered laminate the bundle has the in-plane waviness due to the stitching yarn tension. Due to this waviness the direction of fibers, and, consequently, the direction of the orthotropic axes is variable along the specimen length. Actual values of the

waviness are obtained from experimental data, maximum rotation angle of local orthotropic axes being 13.8°. In order to simulate the bundle waviness precisely, the effect of orthotropic axes rotation is to be included into the model.

An orthotropic material that has the principal material axes rotated by the angle θ (counterclockwise) as shown in Figure 9 is considered. The local matrix of elastic moduli $[\bar{Q}]$ can be calculated by both sides multiplication of the initial elastic moduli matrix $[Q]$ by the rotation matrix $[T]$:

$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}; [\bar{Q}] = [T]^{-1}[Q][T] = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{21} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{61} & \bar{Q}_{62} & 2\bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \theta & \sin^2 \theta & \sin 2\theta \\ \sin^2 \theta & \cos^2 \theta & -\sin 2\theta \\ -\sin 2\theta/2 & \sin 2\theta/2 & \cos 2\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

To include the effect of locally rotated orthotropic elastic properties, an Ansys Parametric Design Language (APDL) code is developed to set the material properties of every finite element in the local coordinate system, according to the experimental measurements.

FE model and boundary conditions

Figure 10. FE model

Figure 11. Fragment of the FE model

The developed FE model (Figures 10-11) of the stitched glassfiber laminate includes two layers of the homogenized bundles, two lightweight 90° layers at the top and the bottom of the specimen, and the epoxy matrix. The model includes the effects of stiffness matrix transformation and local elastic coefficients, caused by the bundles waviness and thickness variation.

378 695 second order 20-node finite elements are used, resulting in the model with 1 579 912 nodes and 4 739 736 degrees of freedom (DOF). Usage of FE model with about $5 \cdot 10^6$ DOF is conditioned by the requirement to study stress concentration near the bundle-matrix interface (determines the cross-section mesh quality) and to describe correctly the longitudinal variation of elastic constants (determines the number of

elements in z-direction). In total, about 400 different orthotropic material properties are used in the developed model to describe variable elastic moduli.

Figure 12. Boundary conditions

Ideal conjunction (continuity of the displacement vector and normal to the interface stress vector) is supposed to be between the bundles and the matrix. Kinematical boundary conditions - longitudinal displacements corresponding to macro-strain $\langle \varepsilon_z \rangle = 0.05\%$ are set at the model boundaries (Figure 12). Such a choice of boundary conditions is defined by an experiment, where the specimen is loaded by setting the displacements at its ends.

FEA Results

Longitudinal stress distribution was obtained for the considered FE model under tension (Figure 13). Stress concentration due to the bundles waviness and non-regular shape is zoomed at Figure 14. Maximum longitudinal stress is reaching $\sigma_{z,max} = 24.4$ MPa. These results were compared to the results obtained for the regular bundle shape (no cross-section variation, constant elastic moduli) - Figure 15. Stress concentration in the regular bundles model turns out to be lower: maximum stress is equal to 21.6 MPa.

Figure 13. Longitudinal stress σ_z distribution, Pa

Figure 14. Stress concentration

Figure 15. Stress concentration for the regular bundles

EXPERIMENTAL FATIGUE TESTS

Three different laminates with different stitching parameters were tested. The laminate is one-sided since a two sided, symmetrical laminate broke always near grip. Such grip failures are not acceptable.

Standard hydraulic material testing machine from MTS was used for UD-laminate fatigue tests (Figure 15). Hydraulic fatigue grips of 100 kN and 25 kN load cell connected in series were used. The 25 kN load cell were employed due to an applied force range of 0.5 ... 2.5 kN.

Figure 15. Damaged test specimen after $3.8 \cdot 10^6$ cycle

All fatigues tests are tension only with $R = 0.1$. The tests are performed using force feedback. Equation (5) is used to calculate an applied frequency and is a function of loading.

$$f_2 = f_1 \cdot \frac{(0.9 \cdot \sigma_1)^2}{(0.9 \cdot \sigma_2)^2} \quad (5)$$

Test specimens were prepared according to ISO 527 standards (Figure 16). Variations in specimen dimensions are accounted by measuring width and thickness from three different spot and using average of these values in calculations.

Before fatigue tests, elastic moduli were measured for all specimens. Measured elastic moduli were used to calculate the failure strength. Failure strength, geometry and chosen loading level were used to calculate the fatigue load.

Figure 16. Test specimen

The elastic modulus varies from 35 GPa to 40 GPa, between test specimens. This is a normal range and is a consequence of variations in fibre volume fraction in width direction of a laminate from where the test specimens are cut. Rapid variation can however effect to test results if the variation occurs inside a test specimen. This happens for example in specimen that is shown in (Figure 17). The SEM-photo reveal some rapid volume changes inside the specimen. This has assumed to cause earlier failure of some specimens.

Figure 17. SEM picture from grip end

Some specimens broke near the grip area and may significantly be out of general trend of the results. All specimens were classified as grip-damaged or clear, correctly damaged specimens. Since it is difficult to say clearly which are grip-damaged and which are correct damaged, some grip-damaged are also accepted. The main goal here is to compare different stitching parameters to each other.

FE MODEL VALIDATION

In this section the static test results and finite element approximations for elastic modulus are compared. Three various glassfibre composites with different stitching

parameters and consequently bundles geometry are considered. Since loading conditions of the fatigue tests are depending also on measurements of elastic modulus the comparison is important. The comparison will also give confidence about finite element model and results obtained.

Mean value of experimental results with maximum and minimum values are shown in (Figure 18). Totally 11 specimen for each model is accounted. The results for finite element model with various combination of transformation of lamina stiffness matrix and local elastic coefficients computation approaches represented.

Figure 18. Dispersion of measured and FEM results in elastic modulus

CONCLUSIONS

FE models of stitched glassfibre composites are created. The models include the effects of stiffness matrix transformation and local elastic coefficients, caused by the bundles waviness and thickness variation. FE simulation is performed, the stress distribution is obtained. Experimental static and fatigue test are also carried out. FE models are validated though the comparison of tests and simulation results. Confidence intervals of elastic moduli obtained from experimental and numerical results are overlapping, what makes it possible to make conclusions about applicability of the developed FE models for the further research of stitched glassfibre composites with various stitching parameters.

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